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RELAZIONE FINALE

Nome e Cognome PI	Jonathan Ford / Alice Affatati (co-PIs)
Titolo del progetto	Source-less seismic: passive acquisition using vessel noise to reduce the impact of geophysical investigation on marine fauna (SLIPSTREAM)

Background

Marine seismic surveys are a fundamental tool for geological research, geohazard characterisation and resource exploration. Conventional acquisition uses active, impulsive sound sources (e.g., airguns or sparkers) that contribute to underwater noise and can have an adverse impact on marine fauna, posing a considerable risk to marine ecosystems. The Technical Group on underwater Noise (TG Noise) has established thresholds for impulsive underwater sound in the framework of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Directive 2008/56/EC). These guidelines state that the maximum fraction of a habitat exposed to impulsive noise higher than the Level of Onset of Biological adverse Effects can be up to 20% or 10% for daily and yearly exposure respectively.

Recent work from industrial seismic exploration has shown that it is possible to acquire source-less marine seismic data using only the continuous noise generated by the acquisition vessel as the sound source, giving images that are comparable to airgun data (Hegna, 2022; [doi:10.3997/1365-2397.fb2022093](https://doi.org/10.3997/1365-2397.fb2022093)). In the SLIPSTREAM project, we aim to understand the geophysical and geological conditions in which source-less acquisition may provide useful seismic images and represent a meaningful reduction in environmental impact, for research-scale acquisition. The overall goal of the development of source-less seismic methods is to lower the exposure of marine fauna to impulsive noise from geophysical research, building on the TG Noise guidelines (Fig. 1).

The SLIPSTREAM project was funded within the iNEST “bando per il finanziamento di progetti di ricerca destinato a giovani ricercatori”. The project duration was from December 2024-February 2026 (extended from the original duration).

Figure 1: Comparison of experimental setup for active source (top) and source-less (bottom) seismic acquisition methods.

Working group and collaborations

The principal investigators for the SLIPSTREAM project are Jonathan Ford and Alice Affatati, both early-career researchers at OGS. The main internal collaborators for the project are the near-surface geophysics group at OGS, led by Luca Baradello and supported by Fabio Meneghini. Martina Busetti contributed geological expertise for planning the field campaign and interpreting the final data.

During the project, an opportunity to collect a deep-water test dataset came thanks to the participation of JF in the MSM135 expedition aboard the R/V Maria San Merian in the Aegean Sea in February 2025. This involved the Marine Geophysics working group at the University of Hamburg (led by Christian Hübscher) and the Marine Geohazards group at Kiel University (Felix Gross).

Objectives

The major focus of the SLIPSTREAM project is to conduct a feasibility study of source-less seismic acquisition in the field using a “research-scale” 2D multi-channel acquisition in shallow water.

The specific objectives included:

1. **A field campaign in the Gulf of Trieste, northeast Italy** to collect a new source-less seismic dataset. The Gulf of Trieste is generally shallow (c. 20 m water depth), and OGS has extensive existing active source “Boomer” data for comparison with the source-less data and in-house expertise. (JF, AA)
2. **Geophysical method development.** Development and testing of new processing flows and algorithms to i) estimate the acoustic signature of the acquisition vessel and ii) deconvolve this signature using the continuous multi-channel streamer recordings. This provides data suitable for conventional seismic processing routines. (JF)

3. **Modelling of the environmental impact.** Acoustic modelling of the impact to regional fauna from both the conventional active source “Boomer” data and the source-less acquisition. (AA)

Figure 2: Map of the profiles collected during the Port of Trieste field campaign (September 2025).

Results and scientific outputs

We successfully completed the SLIPSTREAM field campaign in September 2025. We acquired several source-less seismic profiles within the Port of Trieste using a passenger service vessel (M/B Jonat) and the new multi-channel solid-state streamer from the near-surface geophysics group at OGS (Fig. 2). Raw recordings of ambient and vessel noise from this field test have been submitted to the open-access OPUS portal (The Open Portal to Underwater Soundscapes; <https://opus.ag/>) as an example of acoustic characteristics of a small vessel.

A second opportunity for data collection arose due to the participation of JF on the research cruise MSM135 onboard the R/V Maria San Merian in the Aegean Sea. One short source-less seismic profile was acquired to test deep-water (c. 400 m) acquisition with a longer streamer (100 m), in collaboration with University of Hamburg and Kiel University. The test profile was only partially successful due to the water depth, but we were able to measure some properties of the acoustic characteristics of the vessel, including the use of its waterjet propulsion system. This is significant for future development of the technique as waterjets emit more broadband noise than propellers, improving the bandwidth of the resulting seismic images. This test also functioned as a test of the continuous recording principle (continuous recording using off-the-shelf seismic acquisition systems) and of the robustness of the technique to electrical artefacts, plus initial testing for the data processing routine.

Figure 3: Comparison between source-less and active source Boomer data in the Port of Trieste. (top) Source-less data, after processing (bottom) Active source Boomer data.

During the project, significant progress was made with developing the data processing methodology. After data processing several key geological horizons can be identified (e.g., the base Holocene) and the profiles have comparable sub-seafloor penetration to active source “Boomer” data previously collected in the area (Fig. 3). This method and examples from the Port of Trieste will be published as a scientific article in Ford et al. (in prep). To the best of our knowledge this will be the first published 2D source-less marine seismic dataset.

Work is ongoing on the acoustic impact modelling and assessment, to quantify the reduction in acoustic impact by removing the active impulsive source from the acquisition. Initial modelling work comparing the Boomer and source-less configurations in the Port of Trieste field campaign is now complete. Results show an order-of-magnitude reduction in the areal habitat exposure for bottlenose dolphins, brown meagre, loggerhead turtles and benthic invertebrates. These will be published as a scientific article in Affatati et al. (in prep) and have been included as a chapter of AA’s PhD thesis (Affatati, 2026).

Scientific outputs

Conference abstracts:

- Affatati, A., Baradello, L., Meneghini, F., Buseti, M., Ford, J.; *Source-less marine seismic imaging using vessel noise: a feasibility study in the Port of Trieste, northeast Italy*. To be presented at EGU General Assembly 2026 (Vienna, May 2026).
- Affatati, A., Baradello, L., Meneghini, F., Ford, J.; *Reducing fauna habitat exposure to marine seismic surveys through source-less acquisition*. To be presented at OCEANOISE 2026 (Barcelona, May 2026).

Scientific articles:

- Ford, J., Affatati, A., Meneghini, F., Buseti, M., Baradello, L.; *Source-less Seismic Imaging of Shallow Marine Sediments Using Vessel Noise* (in prep).
- Affatati, A., Baradello, L., Meneghini, F., Ford, J.; *Quantifying the acoustic impact of a source-less research-scale marine seismic survey* (in prep).

PhD thesis chapter:

- Affatati, A. (defended March 2026)

Open-access datasets:

- Ambient and vessel noise dataset submitted to OPUS portal (<https://opus.aq/>)
- SLIPSTREAM field campaign raw data and final processed images to be published open access alongside Ford et al. (in prep) on Zenodo or similar FAIR-compliant data repository

Conclusions

Whilst the main project objectives outlined in the original proposal have been successfully completed, many were significantly delayed due to delays in the arrival of the new seismic streamer of the near-surface geophysics group at OGS, a critical component of the field experiments. This subsequently delayed the completion of many of the scientific outputs, which relied on the field data. Nonetheless, the scientific results obtained so far have exceeded initial expectations and are currently being prepared for publication in the coming months.

Going forward, our future plans include continuing to improve the data processing methodology and the acquisition of further field datasets with different vessels and in different water depths. We currently have a second field campaign planned for Summer 2026 in collaboration with the Marine Geology group at the Geological Survey of Finland, using their waterjet-powered vessel R/V Geomari. This will allow direct comparison between multi-channel source-less and Boomer profiles with a high-resolution 96-channel streamer.

Based on the promising results of the SLIPSTREAM field studies, we envisage that with some further development source-less marine seismics will become a useful method for characterising shallow sub-seafloor sediments, potentially enabling seismic acquisition in ecologically sensitive areas where permits for impulsive sound sources would not be granted.